

THE METHODOLOGY OF SUPPORTING EXERCISES IN TEACHING CLASSICAL TECHNIQUES OF WEIGHT LIFTING IN WEIGHTLIFTING TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: *The article describes the methods of theoretical research, with the support of which the methodology of conducting classes according to the discipline of physical culture with elements of weightlifting has been developed, as well as empirical research methods.*

Keywords: *weightlifting, educational organization of higher education, sports, physical culture, physical culture, exercises, methods of conducting classes*

Sport is an integral part of physical culture aimed at improving the physical and psychological characteristics of a student's personality. Consistency in physical education and sports makes it possible to strengthen health, prolong the life of a person. Weightlifting refers to speed and strength sports, with the performance of weight lifting exercises. With such exercises, the following parts of the body are most involved, and, consequently, the following parts of the body are traumatic: the lower back, knee and shoulder joints. Sport develops discipline and allows you to take a different look at your own body, listen to it more and regularly monitor your health. In turn, lack of physical activity leads to ailments and illnesses.

In the scientific literature of domestic and foreign scientists, a significant number of works are devoted to various aspects of the use of strength exercises in physical education of students. Physical education classes with elements of weightlifting contribute to: the harmonious development of the student; the competent formation of health and physical strength; the combination of knowledge and beauty that determine the place of the individual in the life of society; on the basis of strict discipline and high consciousness, the development of moral and volitional qualities of the individual; an adequate assessment of actions and events without emotions. During classes in the discipline of physical culture with elements of weightlifting, the process of educating students in self-confidence and strength, self-control, responsibility takes place.

It is necessary to study the problem of the influence of strength exercises when performing elements of weightlifting, in classes in the discipline of physical culture, on the change in the physical development of students. Therefore, it is especially necessary to carefully develop a methodology for conducting classes in the discipline of physical culture with elements of weightlifting, contributing to the development and formation of moral, moral-volitional, physical qualities of personality and a healthy lifestyle of students.

Let's consider the developed methodology for conducting an elective course of physical culture and sports with elements of weightlifting. The methodology of such training was developed after analyzing the scientific literature on weightlifting and effective training systems. The purpose of introducing such an elective course into the educational process is to eliminate the deficit of motor activity, as well as the development of the strength of the muscles of the legs, back, shoulder girdle, endurance training.

Teaching methods that are used in such a lesson: verbal (story, conversation); visual (demonstration, observation method); practical (exercises). After greeting and announcing the tasks of the lesson, the teacher conducts a warm-up for the students.

The warm-up consists of:

- a) sports walking;
- b) easy running;
- c) light running with alternating jumps on the left, right legs;
- d) easy running with exercises on a lateral step to the left, to the right sideways, backward with turns to the left, to the right 360 °;
- e) light running with hip-lifting exercise;
- f) light running with exercises for extending the lower leg; jumping up bent and with a 360° turn.
- g) easy running with a transverse step to the left and right sideways;
- h) easy running with jumping up, bending over, with a 360° turn;
- i) easy running, turning into walking.

At this time, the teacher monitors the correctness of the exercises, that is, if students perform the exercises "half-heartedly" or incorrectly, an adjustment is made. The correction is carried out as follows, the teacher announces how this or that exercise is performed correctly, in the case when the students do not understand - shows.

Approximate adjustment of the exercises performed:

- a) students should not run out of order in the process of light running;

b) do not step on the other foot and perform jumps as high as possible during alternate jumps;

c) stick to the formation, look over your right shoulder during light running with side-step exercises;

d) during a light run with an exercise with a high hip lift, try to lift your legs higher and pull up your socks, take a shorter step and raise your knees higher;

e) try to touch the buttocks with your heels during the shin splash exercise;

f) when running lightly with a transverse step, simulate the approach to the throw with a turn;

g) when performing jumps up, bending down, make a jump higher, raise your arms up, bend in the lower back;

h) during the final light run, it should start with acceleration from a low start;

i) when walking, try to regain your breath.

Such a warm-up is customary for physical education classes, it allows you to warm up the necessary muscle groups. After a general warm-up, it is proposed to proceed to specialized exercises in motion to warm up the muscles of the upper shoulder girdle.

Next, students need to perform general developmental exercises on the spot, such as: walking, bending, lunges, splits. Students should perform these exercises with grouping. Teacher's recommendations when performing such exercises:

- the amplitude of the movement should be the largest;

- bends should be performed deeply, the legs should not bend at the knees;

- lunges to do deeper, look at the back of the standing leg;

- perform the march with the greatest amplitude;

- do the exercises clearly and quickly.

The next stage of classes is aimed at teaching students to perform the jerk and push, since this exercise is the main one in weightlifting.

Let's look at the jerk technique, with the features of the phases. The initial phase: it is necessary to stand above the barbell, shoulders should be strictly above the neck, toes under the neck. The legs should be placed shoulder-width apart, the pelvis should be pulled back, the lower back should be bent. Traction phase: In this phase, the barbell is lifted off the floor by the force of the legs and back to the level of the knees. The barbell neck moves towards itself, arms and back are straight. Demolition phase: due to

the full extension of the legs, straightening the trunk on the toes and lifting the shoulders, the barbell accelerates. The hands are in a straight position, the effort should be sharp and powerful. Squat phase: Due to acceleration in the explosion phase, the barbell rises up, the student squats under it. Arms outstretched, hips pressed against the stomach. The lifting phase from the squat: by the effort of the leg muscles, the ascent to the vertical position occurs. The back is bent, the pelvis rises from the bottom up. Fixation phase: the final position, occurs due to the fixation of the barbell on the outstretched arms (jerk) or on the chest (push).

Such exercises in physical education lessons are of great importance, as they are a means to promote the active development of functional systems of the body and physical qualities of students, such as: flexibility, agility, endurance.

Also, these exercises form the tendon-ligament apparatus and are recommended for performance in the main and final parts of the lesson. After demonstrating all the phases of the jerk, the teacher suggests that the students try to perform these exercises in turn. Students who have correctly completed the exercise from the first time are given the opportunity to consolidate the acquired skill independently, under the supervision of a teacher.

Strength is a fundamental physical quality of a person that develops most effectively when using metered weights. Physical education classes with elements of weightlifting can be used to train strength by almost any healthy person without restrictions.

The erroneous opinion is that heaviness is something unaffordable, the "size range" of scales starts from 500 grams, which even a child can do.

Muscle activity during exercises with elements of weightlifting causes increased oxygen consumption by the body, and, consequently, more intensive work of the lungs and heart. From this it can be concluded that together with the tendon-ligamentous and muscular apparatus, the muscles of the main organ of the human body - the heart - develop.

Conclusion. Summing up, it should be said that the discipline of physical culture forms the health of students, the harmonious and comprehensive development of personality interacting in modern society. The elements of weightlifting used in physical education classes contribute to the development of moral and volitional qualities due to strict discipline and the manifestation of consciousness. In the future, it is necessary to develop a set of classes with elements of weightlifting, since systematic and systematic classes in the discipline of physical culture can motivate students to engage

in this sport in their free time, take part in competitions between students of educational institutions of higher education

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